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The Mechanical vs Bio-Spirit-Homo- Technologicus

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Abstract: Five years down the line, things would change a lot from what it is today. The road that we traverse daily won't even give a clue if you skip yourself from that place. The realm of change is out of the bounds and of our hands completely. The interesting factor is that most of these changes does not happen completely by the rudder of our brain. The sophisticated programs that erupted in our brains, flooded onto the technical systems, eventually protruded facts and interesting numbers which made us to fly towards more interesting historical decisions and events. One might ask, can you find a human in midst of these sophisticated turnouts? Well the answer might procure a period of seconds for us, but from a personal perspective, human intervention and the bio-spiritual living is livelier in this era, when the science demands it has reached its peak, as it has always.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), Brain studies, Rationality, Bio-spirit, *Homo technologicus*

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Introduction

What if Artificial intelligence (AI) would baptize your child one day? That would be a highly exaggerated thought, right! But if the unending socialist slogans that were raised during the infancy of the industrialist era could not replace the room size machines from grabbing their jobs, then the day when robots anoint you might not be too exaggerating. But the fact of celibacy and humanity would be a great hurdle for the machine to overcome. Leave out the ‘priest’, just have a thought on the impact happening on earth 50 years from now. Every human is running at 100 miles per hour today. Each being has its targets to be achieved. Once its accomplished new targets are defined, and the cycle goes on. Thus from my perspective, deficiency in genuine relationships are one of the grave drawbacks of this ultra tech era.

This article provides a fringe of knowledge on the influence of AI realm and its implications on the *Homo technologicus*.

Before further analyzing the tragic repercussions brought in by AI, let’s see some of the new acquaintances that turned out to be the welfare and doom for mankind.

The Progress Leading to AI

In this section, we trace the movement from material things like wood and iron to AI and to the possible Superhumans.

From Wood to Iron

The *Homo sapiens* started his traversal of life in woods, which in turn made his life to circle the woods. As humans required more tools for an easier life, he initiated the phenomenon of inventions, both knowingly and unknowingly. At first everything was made of wood and the first ‘wheel,’ was a great invention. Although durable for a certain timeline, the wear and tear of the wooden wheel was always a standing problem.

Then came the molding, casting and shaping which brought forth the iron wheel. The introduction of iron into the daily life brought in a huge change in the living pattern of man.

From Static to Dynamic

The introduction of iron to daily needs was just the beginning. The cyclical motion of iron initiated a big impact, but when it went to the next stage, where the iron parts started to clamor with each other, it inscribed a new history. As Alvin Toffler says in his famous book, 'The third wave', the industrialist era changed the whole face of the earth. Even the word 'success' was properly defined and came into a primal existence in the dynamic era. Before that man's life was simple, doing the daily livelihood works, earn something for the drinks, if felt moody to sit idle the whole day and particularly no great aim. People were in peace and calm and no hurry-burry as that of today. They were contented with their life. But the mechanical era turned everything into a dynamic mood and even the word 'idle' seemed as a blasphemy.

Everyone wanted more, the industrial lives flocked with workers who came in at punctual times. The punctuality which was actually a new code of conduct for the common people eventually came into the pattern to achieve 'more'. The one who is most productive, creative and dynamic was esteemed as successful.

Manual to Automotive

Soon the capitalists realized the manual labour performing repeated work-sets could be replaced by automotive machines. The machines could work on limitlessly without tiring themselves and at the same time would never demand any wages for its labour like humans do. Even though the initial investment was quite high the profit factor, in the long run, stood outstanding. Thus long lines of machines got installed in the workspace, replacing thousands of individual workers. Obviously, strikes were called on against the loss of labour but it could not subdue the strength of the capitalist and machines.

Those who were prudent took up different jobs soon and continued the life pattern. Thus the machine king reigned on evolving itself year after year.

Automotive to AI

The long line of machines was indeed a strength for the industrialists, but every machine installed required a human to do the working, i.e. to control it accordingly. But within a few decades new inventions came up that attached ‘brains’ to the machines which again replaced a good number of labourers. This is the era that has started to work on its own. From washing machines, oven, fridge, television, sound mixers, computers, tablets to table fans, the AI has been driven into whatever things possible, with the caption, to make human life easier. Indeed the human life has become easier because there was a time when a house lady had to walk to stores to procure the stuff she needs, goods been transferred between countries took weeks, communication to be made between different poles on earth took days and even travelling to the nearest metropolitan city took hours, but now the AI has rewritten every concept. Thus, everything has become simpler in terms, but new challenges have risen. What is simpler today does not seem the same tomorrow.

So we are ever striving to make it smaller and cheaper. The competition between the countries is primarily to enhance themselves in artificial intelligence as far as possible because it is what drives everything today.

The IoT (Internet of things) is everywhere and it will be omnipresent in the near future.

Human to Superhuman

This is the future era. Extensive experiments are widely and secretly done in almost all countries, to enhance homo-sapiens. They say humans are vulnerable. Man can be easily manipulated, is highly vulnerable to diseases and has a very

short lifespan. But when it comes to the AI integrated human, the vulnerability can be brought down up to 13%. With further enrichment and experiments the error can be diminished too.

One of the latest news in the tech world is of the famous ‘Reuters’ media group. They have launched their news channel where the news is composed by an AI and at the same time, it is also presented by an AI-developed- character interface. The human intervention here is literally zero. This is not a minor development, because professional news composing and the news reading is not an easy task and normally it takes years for a normal human being to get to the professional level. But the advancement of AI helped it to grab this target too. Humans are relieved of the jobs, which we believed could be done ‘only’ by us.

The Rational Artificial Brain

The basic dictum by which philosophy distinguished man and animal is by ‘man is a rational animal’. But today this rationality can be found in all tech devices. They purely use reason, maybe better than us, to take decisions whereas we humans are lot influenced by our emotions and second thoughts. But for the artificial brain there are no second thoughts, which makes it more rational. Thus what I noted at first, was not just an exaggeration, but their might come a day where the whole mankind will be controlled by the ‘Artificial brain’ for efficient living, which is almost evidently seen in today’s society, like the pre-controlled room temperature, automatically parking cars, auto development of research documents, intruder detection and warning, the list goes on endlessly. Even in medical care there are robots capable of doing a complete surgery without having the smallest intervention of a doctor and at the same time the efficiency of the surgery would be higher than a surgery done by the human hand. But it is a great relief that a ‘heart’ capable of beating like a human heart hasn’t been found yet. If it had been we would have replaced our biological hearts way before.

But ‘stents’ used as a replacement for damaged veins are being experimented and developed with high precision. The people undergoing heart problems find it real helpful with these inventions

to their rescue. In the sequence of Terminator movies, the greatest invention of mankind, i.e. advanced AI for warfare, rationally decides that the mankind which have been inhabiting the mother earth for centuries did not properly take care of the planet earth, rather being as the custodians they lived as the exploiters. And the AI realized if the current pattern continued, humans would simply put the earth to utter destruction. So it decided that the humans is the most tragic creation of all species and it must be exterminated. Thus, the AI comes into war with humans and the humans does their best not to live, but to survive. Eventually they retaliate but soon they realize, attack is the best defense. This is the basic outline of the story and for the past two decades 'Terminator series' is almost telling the same story in different perspectives. They are shouting out the danger of giving an artificial rational brain the freedom to act upon humans.

Humane Artificial Intelligence

The latest hit Malayalam movie '*Android Kunjappan Version 5.25*' speaks of a robot who takes care of the elderly. The film in its first half depicts the care and passion that a robot shows to its master, which is happening because it's coded so. And the film shouts out the human care that's negligibly seen in the present society and how people tend to leave out their parents for a "selfish" comfortable life. But at the end the very limited rational brain of robot reaches its limit and turns out to be a rogue robot and at the same time it makes the master addict to its robotic care.

We develop all mechanisms to give human a better life and the prior concern is always the immediate fruits. In most scenarios the distant effect of a particular project is not analyzed in humanizing ways and the results are not always pleasing. The robotic nursing is already in execution in China, Germany and some other countries. The reports state the results are positive but the ultimate purpose of the machinery is always under question. The machines have become part of our lives such that we humans tend to love more the machines than the beings

around us. This make us less human. We tend to close ourselves in our comfortable boxes and evacuating everything and everyone, who dares to create a pinch of disturbance to us.

The ‘selfie’ culture has been adopted by the society for a few years now. The name itself denotes that selfie gives more importance to the ‘self’. Before the selfie era, people used to take most number of photos in groups, but now everyone focuses on their self. Likewise, a lot many changes have been adapted in the present decade. The virtual media has found its unresisting growth in this era, which has altered even the psychological structure of human thinking. People live in the virtual world today than the reality. People often believe that being approved in the media world is what they want and they try to improvise the virtual world as their reality.

Conclusion

The human brain is not just rational, I would say. It surely is a mix of rational, emotional and surely a ton of second thoughts, and that’s what make us human. We tend to care not because of our rationality but because, the being of human means to care, according to Heidegger. But this care factor is rarely seen these days. As I have mentioned we all are in an accelerated mode trying to achieve more and more. The word ‘enough’ is not inscribed in our dictionary. During this limitless run what we leave back is actually our being. We forget who we are and especially the AI helps a lot to make this happen. There are places were only humans can step in, like relationships, and no AI or sophisticated AI could ever replace this.

Through this paper I was not just trying to relate the AI realm with the human realm but was trying for a floccinaucinihilipilification. I wouldn’t say AI is completely to be banned from human life but it must be stopped or restricted at the pit stops that it is supposed to be stopped. The machines surely make our life easier and we can’t live without it too. Even now I have used ‘Grammarly’, an artificial intelligence platform that corrects grammatic and linguistics errors, to complete my work. The growth factor is inevitable in this era, but it must go hand in hand with the natural cycle of our mother earth.

Humans are being of care, but when AI is allowed to apprehend above the human freedom, danger follows.

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